

Black Mesa Photogrammetry: Whitten

Processing Report

06 April 2023

Survey Data

Fig. 1. Camera locations and image overlap.

Number of images:	152	Camera stations:	152
Flying altitude:	4.44 m	Tie points:	24,925
Ground resolution:	2.91 mm/pix	Projections:	76,739
Coverage area:	494 m ²	Reprojection error:	0.341 pix

Camera Model	Resolution	Focal Length	Pixel Size	Precalibrated
2+ (3.7mm)	4056 x 3040	3.7 mm	1.5 x 1.5 μ m	No

Table 1. Cameras.

Camera Calibration

Fig. 2. Image residuals for 2+ (3.7mm).

2+ (3.7mm)

152 images

Type	Resolution	Focal Length	Pixel Size
Frame	4056 x 3040	3.7 mm	1.5 x 1.5 μm

	Value	Error	F	Cx	Cy	B1	B2	K1	K2	K3	P1	P2
F	2424.18	0.1	1.00	0.04	-0.37	-0.30	-0.02	-0.08	0.18	-0.18	-0.04	-0.16
Cx	12.2481	0.093		1.00	-0.00	0.01	-0.21	0.04	-0.03	0.03	0.82	-0.06
Cy	-8.71689	0.11			1.00	0.06	-0.06	-0.04	-0.01	0.01	0.08	0.56
B1	-28.4891	0.03				1.00	-0.01	-0.05	0.02	-0.01	0.08	0.20
B2	0.536094	0.024					1.00	-0.02	0.01	-0.01	-0.25	-0.04
K1	-0.00623578	8.2e-05						1.00	-0.94	0.87	0.03	-0.16
K2	0.0206451	0.00017							1.00	-0.98	-0.03	0.02
K3	-0.0193655	0.00011								1.00	0.03	-0.02
P1	0.000134303	1.2e-05									1.00	-0.01
P2	0.000419795	1.1e-05										1.00

Table 2. Calibration coefficients and correlation matrix.

Camera Locations

Fig. 3. Camera locations and error estimates.

Z error is represented by ellipse color. X,Y errors are represented by ellipse shape.

Estimated camera locations are marked with a black dot.

X error (cm)	Y error (cm)	Z error (cm)	XY error (cm)	Total error (cm)
18.0976	40.0824	8.08768	43.9786	44.7161

Table 3. Average camera location error.

X - Longitude, Y - Latitude, Z - Altitude.

Ground Control Points

● Control points ⊠ Check points 20 m

Fig. 4. GCP locations and error estimates.

Z error is represented by ellipse color. X,Y errors are represented by ellipse shape.

Estimated GCP locations are marked with a dot or crossing.

Count	X error (cm)	Y error (cm)	Z error (cm)	XY error (cm)	Total (cm)
2	3.7099	4.5951	6.05134	5.90578	8.45559

Table 4. Check points RMSE.

X - Longitude, Y - Latitude, Z - Altitude.

Label	X error (cm)	Y error (cm)	Z error (cm)	Total (cm)	Image (pix)
point 1	-4.35968	4.84885	-6.96437	9.54047	0.372 (79)
point 2	-2.91888	4.3265	-4.97342	7.20926	0.445 (77)
Total	3.7099	4.5951	6.05134	8.45559	0.410

Table 5. Check points.
X - Longitude, Y - Latitude, Z - Altitude.

Scale Bars

Label	Distance (m)	Error (m)
point 1_point 2	0.999967	-3.34935e-05
Total		3.34935e-05

Table 6. Control scale bars.

Digital Elevation Model

Fig. 5. Reconstructed digital elevation model.

Resolution: 1.05 cm/pix
Point density: 0.915 points/cm²

Processing Parameters

General

Cameras	152
Aligned cameras	152
Markers	2
Scale bars	1
Coordinate system	WGS 84 (EPSG::4326)
Rotation angles	Yaw, Pitch, Roll

Point Cloud

Points	24,925 of 134,601
RMS reprojection error	0.14801 (0.3414 pix)
Max reprojection error	0.515008 (1.83887 pix)
Mean key point size	2.27287 pix
Point colors	3 bands, uint8
Key points	737.55 MB
Average tie point multiplicity	5.03089

Alignment parameters

Accuracy	High
Generic preselection	Yes
Reference preselection	Source
Key point limit	60,000
Key point limit per Mpx	1,000
Tie point limit	4,000
Exclude stationary tie points	No
Guided image matching	No
Adaptive camera model fitting	Yes
Matching time	2 minutes 22 seconds
Matching memory usage	847.80 MB
Alignment time	1 minutes 22 seconds
Alignment memory usage	64.60 MB

Optimization parameters

Parameters	f, b1, b2, cx, cy, k1-k3, p1, p2
Adaptive camera model fitting	Yes
Optimization time	0 seconds
Date created	2022:11:01 16:19:19
Software version	1.8.3.14298
File size	13.89 MB

Depth Maps

Count	144
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Depth maps generation parameters

Quality	High
Filtering mode	Mild
Max neighbors	16
Processing time	8 minutes 9 seconds
Memory usage	3.05 GB
Date created	2022:11:01 16:34:56
Software version	1.8.3.14298
File size	567.47 MB

Dense Point Cloud

Points	22,773,815
Point colors	3 bands, uint8

Depth maps generation parameters	
Quality	High
Filtering mode	Mild
Max neighbors	16
Processing time	8 minutes 9 seconds
Memory usage	3.05 GB
Dense cloud generation parameters	
Processing time	12 minutes 51 seconds
Memory usage	7.47 GB
Date created	2022:11:01 16:39:50
Software version	1.8.3.14298
File size	514.49 MB
Model	
Faces	6,443,710
Vertices	3,229,016
Vertex colors	3 bands, uint8
Texture	8,192 x 8,192, 4 bands, uint8
Depth maps generation parameters	
Quality	High
Filtering mode	Mild
Max neighbors	16
Processing time	8 minutes 9 seconds
Memory usage	3.05 GB
Reconstruction parameters	
Surface type	Arbitrary
Source data	Dense cloud
Interpolation	Enabled
Strict volumetric masks	No
Processing time	7 minutes 38 seconds
Memory usage	7.40 GB
Texturing parameters	
Mapping mode	Generic
Blending mode	Mosaic
Texture size	8,192
Enable hole filling	Yes
Enable ghosting filter	Yes
UV mapping time	1 minutes 21 seconds
UV mapping memory usage	3.16 GB
Blending time	1 minutes 16 seconds
Blending memory usage	3.30 GB
Blending GPU memory usage	2.22 GB
Date created	2022:11:01 19:14:07
Software version	1.8.3.14298
File size	359.61 MB
System	
Software name	Agisoft Metashape Professional
Software version	1.8.0 build 13794
OS	Windows 64 bit
RAM	31.85 GB
CPU	Intel(R) Core(TM) i7-6920HQ CPU @ 2.90GHz
GPU(s)	Quadro M2200